

Appendix

This appendix provides the complete set of all 29 combinatorial formulas used to count all typed graphlets of up to 5 nodes. Our implementation is available in the accompanying repository: <https://github.com/c-beth/CaTSCAN> (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20555447>)

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A Notation

The following terms are used across the formulas to count typed 3-, 4-, or 5-node graphlets according to Problem 1.

Summary of Notation (Repetition of Table 1)

Symbol	Meaning
$G = (V, E, \mathcal{T}_V, \tau)$	HIN G with nodes V , edges E , types \mathcal{T}_V , type map τ
$\tau : V \mapsto \mathcal{T}_V$	Maps each node v to its type t
$v_i, v_j, v_k, v_l, v_r \in V$	Nodes in V with labels i, j, k, l, r
$e_{ij} = \{v_i, v_j\} \in E$	Undirected edge connecting nodes v_i and v_j
$\mathcal{N}(v_i), \mathcal{N}_t(v_i)$	Neighbors of v_i , neighbors of v_i with type t
$\vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i), \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$	Out-, in-neighbors of node v_i in DAG representation
$\text{deg}(v_i), \text{deg}_t(v_i)$	Total degree of v_i , degree of v_i w.r.t. type t
$v_i \prec v_j$	v_i is smaller than v_j w.r.t. to degree ordering
$G_{\prec} = (V, E_{\prec}, \mathcal{T}_V, \tau)$	DAG version of G with degree-oriented edges E_{\prec}
Γ, γ	Node-typed graphlet Γ , instance γ
$T, T_{\Gamma} \in \mathcal{T}_V^k$	a type vector, the representative type vector for Γ
$M : \mathcal{T}_V^k \mapsto \mathbb{Z}$	Count map mapping type vectors to counts
$ M $	Number of unique typizations in M
$\Delta_t(e), \Delta_{t,t'}(v_i)$	Number of triangles formed at e, v_i by type(s) t, t'

Terms returning node sets for iterating through all relevant instances of a graphlet:

- $\Delta(v_i, v_j)$: all nodes $v_k \in V$ that form a triangle with v_i and v_j
- $\mathcal{C}(v_i, v_j, v_k)$: all nodes $v_r \in V$ forming a 4-clique with the triangle (v_i, v_j, v_k)

Terms returning counts for directly computing graphlet frequencies:

- $\text{deg}_{t_0|\mathcal{T}}(v_i)$: typed degree of v_i w.r.t. to type $t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V$, decreased by 1 for each match $t_0 = t_1$ for type t_1 in type multiset \mathcal{T}
- $\mathcal{W}_{\vec{t}_0}(v_i, v_k)$: number of out-out wedges centered at a node of type $t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V$ and having $v_i, v_k \in V$ as remaining nodes
- $\mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t}_0}(v_i, v_k)$: number of in-out wedges centered at a node of type $t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V$ and having $v_i, v_k \in V$ as remaining nodes
- $\mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_k)$: number of out-out and in-out wedges centered at a node of type $t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V$ and having $v_i, v_k \in V$ as remaining nodes
- $\Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)$: number of nodes of type t_0 forming a triangle with the nodes $v_i, v_j \in V$
- $\Delta_{t_0|\mathcal{T}}(v_i, v_j)$: $\Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)$, decreased by 1 for each match $t_0 = t_1$ for type t_1 in type multiset \mathcal{T}
- $\Delta_{t_0, t_1}(v_i)$: number of triangles node $v_i \in V$ forms with nodes of types $t_0, t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V$

- $\mathcal{D}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j, v_k)$: number of nodes of type $t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V$ that form a diamond centered at edge v_j and the node of type t_0 (meaning that edges $(v_j, v_i), (v_j, v_k) \in E$ as well as edges from the node of type t_0 to v_i, v_j, v_k exist)
- $\mathcal{C}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j, v_k)$: number of nodes of type t_0 that form a 4-clique with the triangle (v_i, v_j, v_k)

B Counting Typed 3-Node Graphlets

All typed 3-node graphlets can be counted in

$$\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\Delta}}| + |V| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2)$$

time with $\mathcal{O}(1)$ additional space, omitting result size and the CSR-graph.

B.1 Wedge

The wedge graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacktriangle} .

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\blacktriangle} := & \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\ & \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \right) \end{aligned}$$

All typed wedges can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2)$ time.

B.2 Triangle

The triangle graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\triangle} . The computation of M_{\triangle} differs from the provided code to improve readability while effectively doing the same. Instead of selecting $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$, the code selects $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$ with the bonus criteria that an edge between v_j and v_k exists and that $(v_i, v_j) < (v_i, v_k)$. Both statements allow to only consider each triangle once and are thus equivalent, the statement in the code is just more efficient to compute while the statement in M_{\triangle} is easier to read.

$$M_{\triangle} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{\substack{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \\ v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \\ \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)}} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k)), 1 \right)$$

All typed triangles can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\Delta}})$ time.

C Counting Typed 4-Node Graphlets

All typed 4-node graphlets can be counted in

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{O}((|\mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{\Delta}}| + |\mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{\Delta}}|) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 \\ & \quad + |E| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 \\ & \quad + |V| \cdot (\Delta_{\max} \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| + |\mathcal{T}_V|^2) \\ & \quad + DD + |M_{\Delta}|) \end{aligned}$$

time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles a node is participating in, and DD denotes the number of directed diamonds as described in [18]. The additional space requirement is in $\mathcal{O}((|V| + |E|) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|)$.

C.1 3-Star

The 3-star graphlet is computed by the count map $M_{\bullet, \bullet, \bullet}$.

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\bullet, \bullet, \bullet} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0, t_0), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{3} \right) \\ &\quad \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0, t_1), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{2} \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \right) \\ &\quad \oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_1), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_1}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\ &\quad \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 < t_2}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_2}(v_i) \right) \end{aligned}$$

All typed 3-stars $\bullet, \bullet, \bullet$ can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^3)$ time.

C.2 3-Path

The 3-path graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\curvearrowright} . When counting 3-path graphlets, each instance of the triangle graphlet is counted 3 times without creating a 3-path. Therefore, for each triangle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\curvearrowright C}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\curvearrowright B}$ to obtain the correct count of 3-paths, i.e., $M_{\curvearrowright} := M_{\curvearrowright B} \oplus M_{\curvearrowright C}$.

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\curvearrowright B} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\ & \quad M \left((t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_1), \deg_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_j) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$M_{\blacktriangleright C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2), c) \in M_{\triangle}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_1), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_2, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c)$$

All typed 3-paths \blacktriangleright can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\triangle}|)$ time, where $|M_{\triangle}|$ denotes the number of unique triangle typizations that exist in the graph.

C.3 4-Cycle

The 4-cycle graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} . The computation of M_{\blacklozenge} differs from the provided code to improve readability. It does not explicitly create the set of all wedges in which nodes participate, but rather assumes it is present. To further improve readability, $v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_j)$ is chosen over separately choosing $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$ followed by checking if $v_k \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$ as in the code.

$$M_{\blacklozenge} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_j)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, \tau(v_k), t_0), \binom{\mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_k)}{2} \right) \\ \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M((\tau(v_i), t_0, \tau(v_k), t_1), \mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \mathcal{W}_{t_1}(v_i, v_k))$$

All typed 4-cycles \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}((|\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\triangleright}}| + |\mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{\triangleright}}|) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2)$ time.

C.4 Tailed Triangle

The tailed triangle graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacktriangleright} . The computation of M_{\blacktriangleright} differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code directly retrieves the types t_1, t_2 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure and does not need to iterate over the respective type loops. Also, the criterion $t_1 \leq t_2$ is not needed in the code base as each type combination is only considered once within this data structure.

$$M_{\blacktriangleright} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V \\ t_1 \leq t_2}} \sum_{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2), \deg_{t_0 \{t_1, t_2\}}(v_i) \cdot \Delta_{t_1, t_2}(v_i) \right)$$

All typed tailed triangles \blacktriangleright can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| \cdot \Delta_{\max})$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles a node participates in.

C.5 Diamond

The diamond graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\diamond} .

$$M_{\diamond} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_0), \binom{\Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \right) \\ \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_1), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j))$$

All typed diamonds \diamond can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2)$ time.

C.6 4-Clique

The 4-clique graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\diamond} . The computation of M_{\diamond} differs from the provided code to improve readability while effectively doing the same. Instead of selecting $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$, the code selects $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$ with the bonus criteria that an edge between v_j and v_k exists and that $(v_i, v_j) < (v_i, v_k)$. Both statements allow to only consider each triangle once and are thus equivalent, the statement in the code is just more efficient to compute while the statement in M_{\diamond} is easier to read. Further, the code base creates a structure containing all nodes $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$ to efficiently retrieve v_k and v_r , by selecting v_r stored at larger indices than v_k within that structure and checking if an edge between v_j and v_k exists. The provided formula does the same by only checking out-edges of v_k as this also ensures an ordering while checking for an edge between v_k and v_r .

$$M_{\diamond} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \\ \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \\ \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j) \\ \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_k)}} M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r)), 1)$$

All typed 4-cliques \diamond can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\Delta}}| + DD)$ time, where DD is the number of directed diamonds as described in [18].

D Counting Typed 5-Node Graphlets

All typed 5-node graphlets can be counted in

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}| \cdot (\Delta_{\max}^2 \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| + \deg_{\max}) \\
& + |E| \cdot (\Delta_{\max}^2 \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |\mathcal{T}_V|^3) \\
& + |V| \cdot (\Delta_{\max}^2 + (\deg_{\max} + \Delta_{\max}) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |\mathcal{T}_V|^4) \\
& + |\Delta| \cdot (\deg_{\max} + |\mathcal{T}_V|^2) \\
& + DD \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| + DBP + D \\
& + |M_{\blacktriangleleft\blacktriangleright}| + |M_{\blacklozenge}| + |M_{\blacktriangle}| + |M_{\blacklozenge}| + |M_{\blacklozenge}|)
\end{aligned}$$

time, where \deg_{\max} denotes the maximum degree of a node in the graph, Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles a node or edge are participating in, DD denotes the number of directed diamonds as described in [18], D denotes the total number of diamonds as described in [18], and DBP denotes the number of directed bipyramids as described in [18]. The additional space requirement is in $\mathcal{O}((|V| + |E|) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| + |\Delta|)$.

D.1 4-Star

The 4-star graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} .

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\blacklozenge} & := \\
& \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0, t_0, t_0), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{4} \right) \\
& \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0, t_0, t_1), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{3} \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \right) \\
& \quad \oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0, t_1, t_1), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{2} \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_1}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\
& \quad \oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_1, t_1), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_1}(v_i)}{3} \right) \\
& \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 < t_2}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_0, t_1, t_2), \binom{\deg_{t_0}(v_i)}{2} \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_2}(v_i) \right) \\
& \quad \oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_1, t_2), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_1}(v_i)}{2} \cdot \deg_{t_2}(v_i) \right) \\
& \quad \oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2, t_2), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_2}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\
& \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_3 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_2 < t_3}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), \deg_{t_0}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_1}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_2}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_3}(v_i) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

All typed 4-stars \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^4)$ time.

D.2 Prong

The prong graphlet is computed by the count map $M_{\mathfrak{Y}}$. When counting prong graphlets, each instance of the tailed triangle graphlet is counted twice without creating a prong. Therefore, for each tailed triangle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\mathfrak{Y}C}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\mathfrak{Y}B}$ to obtain the correct count of 3-paths, i.e., $M_{\mathfrak{Y}} := M_{\mathfrak{Y}B} \oplus M_{\mathfrak{Y}C}$.

$$M_{\mathfrak{Y}B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_1, t_1), \deg_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_j)}{2} \right) \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 < t_2}} M \left((t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_1, t_2), \deg_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_j) \cdot \deg_{t_2|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_j) \right)$$

$$M_{\mathfrak{Y}C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\mathfrak{Y}C}} M((t_2, t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_3, t_2, t_0, t_1, t_3), -c)$$

All typed prongs \mathfrak{Y} can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^3 + |M_{\mathfrak{Y}C}|)$ time.

D.3 4-Path

The 4-path graphlet is computed by the count map $M_{\mathfrak{P}}$. When counting 4-path graphlets, each instance of the 4-cycle graphlet is counted four times without creating a 4-path. Therefore, for each 4-cycle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\mathfrak{P}C_1}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\mathfrak{P}B}$. Also, each instance of the tailed triangle graphlet is counted twice without creating a 4-path. Therefore, for each tailed triangle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\mathfrak{P}C_2}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\mathfrak{P}B}$. Also, each instance of the triangle graphlet is counted three times without creating a 4-path. Therefore, for each triangle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\mathfrak{P}C_3}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\mathfrak{P}B}$. Leading to the final formula $M_{\mathfrak{P}} := M_{\mathfrak{P}B} \oplus M_{\mathfrak{P}C_1} \oplus M_{\mathfrak{P}C_2} \oplus M_{\mathfrak{P}C_3}$.

Also, the computation of $M_{\mathfrak{P}}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability while effectively doing the same. The code base fills data structures to efficiently retrieve pairs of node types creating wedges starting at node v_i that are then combined to create the 4-path. The $M_{\mathfrak{P}}$ -formula manually creates these wedges by selecting the center nodes v_j and v_k and extending them with

the types t_0 and t_1 to create the wedges starting at node v_i .

$$M_{\diamond B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_i) \\ v_j < v_k}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M(t_0, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_1, \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_j) \cdot \text{deg}_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_k))$$

$$M_{\diamond C_1} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_2, t_3, t_0, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_2, t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), -c)$$

$$M_{\diamond C_2} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_3, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_3, t_2, t_0), -c)$$

$$M_{\diamond C_3} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2), c) \in M_{\Delta}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_0, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_2, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_2, t_0, t_1, t_2, t_0), -c)$$

All typed 4-paths can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot \text{deg}_{\max} \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\diamond}| + |M_{\diamond}^{\downarrow}| + |M_{\Delta}|)$ time.

D.4 Forked-Tailed Triangle

The forked-tailed triangle graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\bowtie} . The computation of M_{\bowtie} differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code directly retrieves the types t_0, t_1 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure and does not need to iterate over the respective type loops. Also, the criterion $t_0 \leq t_1$ is not needed in the code base as each type combination is only considered once within this data structure.

$$M_{\bowtie} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V \\ t_0 \leq t_1}} \sum_{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M\left(\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2, t_2, \Delta_{t_0, t_1}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\text{deg}_{t_2|\{t_0, t_1\}}(v_i)}{2}\right) \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_3 \in \mathcal{T}_V \\ t_2 \leq t_3}} M\left(\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, \Delta_{t_0, t_1}(v_i) \cdot \text{deg}_{t_2|\{t_0, t_1\}}(v_i) \cdot \text{deg}_{t_3|\{t_0, t_1\}}(v_i)\right)$$

All typed forked-tailed triangles \bowtie can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot \Delta_{\max} \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2)$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles a node is participating in.

D.5 Long-Tailed Triangle

The long-tailed triangle graphlet is computed by the count map M_{∇} . When counting long-tailed triangle graphlets, each instance of the diamond graphlet is counted four times without creating a long-tailed triangle. Therefore, for each diamond identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\nabla C_1}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\nabla B}$. Also, each instance of the tailed triangle graphlet is counted twice without creating a long-tailed triangle. Therefore, for each tailed triangle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\nabla C_2}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\nabla B}$. Also, each instance of the triangle graphlet is counted six times without creating a long-tailed triangle. Therefore, for each triangle identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\nabla C_3}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\nabla B}$. Leading to the final formula $M_{\nabla} := M_{\nabla B} \oplus M_{\nabla C_1} \oplus M_{\nabla C_2} \oplus M_{\nabla C_3}$.

Further, the computation of M_{∇} differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code directly retrieves the types t_0, t_1 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure and does not need to iterate over the respective type loops. Also, the criterion $t_0 \leq t_1$ is not needed in the code base as each type combination is only considered once within this data structure.

$$M_{\nabla B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V \\ t_0 \leq t_1}} \sum_{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((t_2, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), t_0, t_1), \Delta_{t_0, t_1}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\deg_{t_2|\{\tau(v_i)\}}(v_j)}{2} \right)$$

$$M_{\nabla C_1} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_0, t_2, t_1, t_0, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_0, t_3, t_1, t_0, t_2), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_1, t_2, t_0, t_1, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c)$$

$$M_{\nabla C_2} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\blacklozenge}} M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_0, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_3, t_0, t_2), -c)$$

$$M_{\nabla C_3} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2), c) \in M_{\triangle}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_0, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_0, t_2, t_1, t_0, t_2), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_0, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_2, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_2, t_0, t_1, t_0, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_2, t_1, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c)$$

All typed long-tailed triangles ∇ can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot \Delta_{\max} \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| + |M_{\diamond}| + |M_{\blacklozenge}| + |M_{\triangle}|)$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles a node participates in.

D.6 Double-Tailed Triangle

The double-tailed triangle graphlet is computed by the count map $M_{\hat{\triangle}}$. When counting double-tailed triangle graphlets, each instance of the diamond graphlet is counted twice without creating a double-tailed triangle. Therefore, for each diamond identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\hat{\triangle}C}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\hat{\triangle}B}$, i.e., $M_{\hat{\triangle}} := M_{\hat{\triangle}B} \oplus M_{\hat{\triangle}C}$.

Further, the computation of $M_{\hat{\triangle}}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code directly retrieves the type t_0 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure.

$$M_{\hat{\triangle}B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{N}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_1, t_2), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{t_0, \tau(v_j)\}}(v_i) \cdot \deg_{t_2|\{t_0, \tau(v_i)\}}(v_j) \right)$$

$$M_{\hat{\triangle}C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_0, t_1, t_3, t_2, t_2), -c)$$

All typed double-tailed triangles $\hat{\triangle}$ can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot \Delta_{\max} \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\diamond}|)$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles an edge is adjacent to.

D.7 Tailed 4-Cycle

The tailed 4-cycle graphlet is created by 4 base formulas $M_{\diamond B_1}$, $M_{\diamond B_2}$ and $M_{\diamond B_3}$. When counting tailed 4-cycle graphlets, each instance of the diamond graphlet is counted twice without creating a tailed 4-cycle. Therefore, for each diamond identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\diamond C}$ must be applied to the base count maps, i.e., $M_{\diamond} := M_{\diamond B_1} \oplus M_{\diamond B_2} \oplus M_{\diamond B_3} \oplus M_{\diamond C}$.

Further, the computation of M_{\diamond} differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code computes the base counts within nested loops in the code base, while the provided formula break the computation down to different base terms to avoid long formulas with many parentheses. Also, the provided formulas do not explicitly create the sets of all out-out and in-out wedges in which nodes

participate, but rather assume they are present.

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\diamond B_1} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \overrightarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j) \\ v_i < v_k}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
&M \left((t_1, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, \tau(v_k)), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \frac{\deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j), t_0\}}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k)\}}(v_j) \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_k), \tau(v_j), t_0, \tau(v_i)), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \frac{\deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j), t_0\}}(v_k)}{2} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\diamond B_2} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \overrightarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j) \\ v_k \neq v_i}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
&M \left((t_1, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, \tau(v_k)), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j), t_0\}}(v_i) \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k)\}}(v_j) \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_k), \tau(v_j), t_0, \tau(v_i)), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j), t_0\}}(v_k) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\diamond B_3} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{v_k \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
&M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k)\}}(v_j) \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, \tau(v_k)), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \frac{\deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j), t_0\}}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k)\}}(v_j) \right) \\
&\oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_k), \tau(v_j), t_0, \tau(v_i)), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \frac{\deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j), t_0\}}(v_k)}{2} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$M_{\diamond C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_3, t_1), -c)$$

All typed tailed 4-cycles \diamond can be counted in $\mathcal{O}((|\mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}}| + |\mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}}|) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\diamond}| + |M_{\diamond}|)$ time.

D.8 5-Cycle

The 5-cycle graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\diamond} . The 5-cycle is overcounted by instances of the tailed triangle graphlet. Therefore, the correction

term $M_{\diamond C_1}$ and $M_{\diamond C_2}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\diamond B}$, i.e., $M_{\diamond} := M_{\diamond B} \oplus M_{\diamond C_1} \oplus M_{\diamond C_2}$.

Further, the computation of M_{\diamond} differs from the provided code to improve readability. It does not explicitly create the set of all wedges in which nodes participate, but rather assumes it is present. Both correction terms, $M_{\diamond C_1}$ and $M_{\diamond C_2}$, are computed within the nested loops computing the base count $M_{\diamond B}$ in the code base, while the provided formula break the computation down to different correction terms to avoid long formulas with many parentheses.

$$M_{\diamond B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_k): \\ v_i \neq v_r \\ v_j \neq v_r}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M(\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), t_0, \mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_r))$$

$$M_{\diamond C_1} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j) \\ \cap \mathcal{N}(v_i)}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_k): \\ v_i \neq v_r \\ v_j \neq v_r}} M(\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_k)), -1)$$

$$M_{\diamond C_2} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j) \\ \cap \mathcal{N}(v_j)}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_k): \\ v_i \neq v_r}} M(\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_j)), -1)$$

All typed 5-cycles \diamond can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\triangle}}| \cdot \deg_{\max} \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V| + |\mathcal{W}_{\underline{\triangle}}|)$ time.

D.9 Hourglass

The hourglass graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\bowtie} . When counting hourglass graphlets, each instance of the diamond graphlet is counted twice without creating an hourglass. Therefore, for each diamond identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\bowtie C}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\bowtie B}$, i.e., $M_{\bowtie} := M_{\bowtie B} \oplus M_{\bowtie C}$.

Further, the computation of $M_{\bowtie B}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code directly retrieves the types t_0, t_1 and t_2, t_3 of the triangles together with the count from a data structure and does not need to iterate over the respective type loops. Therefore, in the code the second triangle of types t_2, t_3 is chosen by the next position after the position of the first triangle of types t_0, t_1 in the data structure instead of explicitly choosing $t_0 < t_2$ as a criterion for not counting occurrences of the graphlet twice. Also, the criteria $t_0 \leq t_1$ and $t_2 \leq t_3$ are not needed in the code base as each type combination is only considered once

within this data structure.

$$M_{\bowtie B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 \leq t_1}} M \left((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_0, t_1), \binom{\Delta_{t_0, t_1}(v_i)}{2} \right) \\ \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_2}} \sum_{\substack{t_3 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_2 \leq t_3}} M((\tau(v_i), t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), \Delta_{t_0, t_1}(v_i) \cdot \Delta_{t_2, t_3}(v_i))$$

$$M_{\bowtie C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\bowtie}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_1, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_0, t_3), -c)$$

All typed hourglasses \bowtie can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|V| \cdot \Delta_{\max}^2 + |M_{\bowtie}|)$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number triangles a node participates in.

D.10 Cobra

The cobra graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\diamond} . When counting cobra graphlets, each instance of the 4-clique graphlet is counted twelve times without creating a cobra. Therefore, for each 4-clique identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\diamond C}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\diamond B}$, i.e., $M_{\diamond} := M_{\diamond B} \oplus M_{\diamond C}$.

Further, the computation of $M_{\diamond B}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code uses $v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$ followed by a check if $\deg(i) > \deg(j)$ or if $\deg(i) = \deg(j)$ and $i > j$ as the index of the undirected edge is needed. This formula simplifies this notation by choosing $v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$. The code also directly retrieves the type t_0 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure.

$$M_{\diamond B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \\ \Delta(v_i, v_j)}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((t_1, \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0), \Delta_{t_0|\{\tau(v_k)\}}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \deg_{t_1|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j)\}}(v_k) \right)$$

$$M_{\diamond C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_0, t_2, t_1, t_3, t_0), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_0, t_3, t_1, t_2, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_3, t_1), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_1, t_2, t_0, t_3, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_3, t_0, t_2, t_1), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_2, t_0, t_1, t_3, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_2, t_1, t_0, t_3, t_2), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_2, t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_3, t_1, t_0, t_2, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_3, t_2, t_0, t_1, t_3), -c)$$

All typed cobras \diamond can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\Delta| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\diamond}|)$ time.

D.11 Stingray

The stingray graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\diamond} .

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\diamond} := & \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
& M \left((t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_1, t_1), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j), t_1, t_1\}}(v_i) \cdot \binom{\Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \right) \\
& \oplus M \left((t_0, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), t_1, t_1), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_i), t_1, t_1\}}(v_j) \cdot \binom{\Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \right) \\
\oplus & \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 \leq t_2}} M \left((t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_1, t_2), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j), t_1, t_2\}}(v_i) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_2}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\
& \oplus M \left((t_0, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), t_1, t_2), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_i), t_1, t_2\}}(v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_2}(v_i, v_j) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

All typed stingrays \diamond can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^3)$ time.

D.12 Hatted 4-Cycle

The hatted 4-cycle graphlet is created by 3 base formulas $M_{\hat{\diamond}B_1}$, $M_{\hat{\diamond}B_2}$ and $M_{\hat{\diamond}B_3}$. When counting hatted 4-cycle graphlets, each instance of the diamond graphlet is counted four times without creating a hatted 4-cycle. Therefore, for each diamond identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\hat{\diamond}C}$ must be applied to the base count maps, i.e., $M_{\hat{\diamond}} := M_{\hat{\diamond}B_1} \oplus M_{\hat{\diamond}B_2} \oplus M_{\hat{\diamond}B_3} \oplus M_{\hat{\diamond}C}$.

Further, the computation of $M_{\hat{\diamond}}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code computes the base counts within nested loops in the code base, while the provided formula break the computation down to different base terms to avoid long formulas with many parentheses. Also, the provided formulas do not explicitly create the sets of all out-out and in-out wedges in which nodes participate, but rather assume they are present.

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\hat{\diamond}B_1} := & \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \overrightarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j): \\ v_i \neq v_k}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
& M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\
\oplus & M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_j, v_k) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\hat{\triangleleft} B_2} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{\substack{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \\ v_i < v_j}} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \overrightarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j) \\ v_i < v_k}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
&\quad M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\
&\quad \oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_j, v_k) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\hat{\triangleleft} B_3} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{v_k \in \overleftarrow{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
&\quad M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\
&\quad \oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\
&\quad \oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_j, v_k) \right) \\
&\quad \oplus M \left((t_1, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}}(v_i, v_k) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_j, v_k) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\hat{\triangleleft} C} &:= \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\hat{\triangleleft} C}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_0, t_1, t_3, t_2, t_0), -c) \\
&\quad \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_3, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_3, t_2, t_1), -c)
\end{aligned}$$

All typed hatted 4-cycles $\hat{\triangleleft}$ can be counted in $\mathcal{O}((|\mathcal{W}_{\overrightarrow{t_0}}| + |\mathcal{W}_{\overleftarrow{t_0}}|) \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\hat{\triangleleft} C}|)$ time.

D.13 3-Wedge-Collision

The 3-wedge-collision graphlet is computed by the count map $M_{\hat{\triangleleft} \triangleright}$. Further, the computation of $M_{\hat{\triangleleft} \triangleright}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability. It does not explicitly create the set of all wedges in which nodes participate, but rather assumes it is present.

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\hat{\triangleleft} \triangleright} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_k)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_0, t_0), \binom{\mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)}{3} \right) \\
&\quad \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_0, t_1), \binom{\mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \cdot \mathcal{W}_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\
&\quad \oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_1, t_1), \mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \binom{\mathcal{W}_{t_1}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \right) \\
&\quad \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 < t_2}} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_1, t_2), \mathcal{W}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \mathcal{W}_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \mathcal{W}_{t_2}(v_i, v_j) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

All typed 3-wedge collisions \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^3)$ time.

D.14 3-Triangle-Collision

The 3-triangle-collision graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} .

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\blacklozenge} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_0, t_0), \binom{\Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)}{3} \right) \\ &\oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_0, t_1), \binom{\Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \right) \\ &\oplus M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_1, t_1), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \binom{\Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j)}{2} \right) \\ &\oplus \sum_{\substack{t_2 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 < t_2}} M \left((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0, t_1, t_2), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_1}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_2}(v_i, v_j) \right) \end{aligned}$$

All typed 3-triangle-collisions \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^3)$ time.

D.15 Tailed 4-Clique

The tailed 4-clique graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} . The computation of M_{\blacklozenge} differs from the provided code to improve readability while effectively doing the same. The code base creates a data structure containing all nodes $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i) \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$ to efficiently retrieve v_k without having to check $v_i < v_k$ and $v_j < v_k$. The code base uses the same structure to efficiently retrieve nodes v_r forming 4-cliques with v_i, v_j and v_r , where $v_k < v_r$ is equivalent to the position of v_k being before the position of v_r in the data structure, as both conditions avoid consideration of duplicates.

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\blacklozenge} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \\ v_i < v_k \\ v_j < v_k}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \\ v_k < v_r}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\ &M \left(t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r) \right), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r)\}}(v_i) \\ &\oplus M \left(t_0, \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r) \right), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r)\}}(v_j) \\ &\oplus M \left(t_0, \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r) \right), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r)\}}(v_k) \\ &\oplus M \left(t_0, \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k) \right), \text{deg}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k)\}}(v_r) \end{aligned}$$

All typed tailed 4-cliques \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\blacklozenge}}| + DD \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|)$ time, where DD is the number of directed diamonds as described in [18].

D.16 Triangle-Strip

The triangle-strip graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\triangleright} . When counting triangle-strip graphlets, each instance of the 4-clique graphlet is counted twelve times without creating a triangle-strip. Therefore, for each 4-clique identified by the type vector (t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3) occurring c times, the correction term $M_{\triangleright C}$ must be applied to the base count map $M_{\triangleright B}$, i.e., $M_{\triangleright} := M_{\triangleright B} \oplus M_{\triangleright C}$.

Further, the computation of $M_{\triangleright B}$ differs from the provided code to improve readability while effectively doing the same. Instead of selecting $v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_i) \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)$, the code selects $v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)$ with the bonus criteria that an edge between v_j and v_k exists and that $(v_i, v_j) < (v_i, v_k)$. Both statements allow to only consider each triangle once and are thus equivalent, the statement in the code is just more efficient to compute while the statement in $M_{\triangleright B}$ is easier to read. Also, the code directly retrieves the types t_0/t_1 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure.

$$M_{\triangleright B} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \mathcal{N}(v_i): \\ \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_j)}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \sum_{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M(\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), t_0, t_1, \Delta_{t_0|\{\tau(v_k)\}}(v_i, v_j) \cdot \Delta_{t_1|\{\tau(v_j)\}}(v_i, v_k))$$

$$M_{\triangleright C} := \sum_{((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3), c) \in M_{\diamond}} M((t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_2, t_3, t_3), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_2, t_0, t_1, t_3, t_3), -c) \oplus M((t_0, t_1, t_3, t_2, t_2), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_1, t_0, t_3, t_2, t_2), -c) \oplus M((t_3, t_0, t_1, t_2, t_2), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_0, t_2, t_3, t_1, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_2, t_0, t_3, t_1, t_1), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_3, t_0, t_2, t_1, t_1), -c) \oplus M((t_1, t_2, t_3, t_0, t_0), -c) \\ \oplus M((t_2, t_1, t_3, t_0, t_0), -c) \oplus M((t_3, t_1, t_2, t_0, t_0), -c)$$

All typed triangle-strips \triangleright can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\Delta| \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2 + |M_{\diamond}|)$ time.

D.17 Chordal-Wedge-Collision

The chordal-wedge-collision graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\diamond} . The computation of M_{\diamond} differs from the provided code to improve readability. It does not explicitly create the set of all wedges in which nodes participate, but rather assumes it is present. Further, the code base does not assume that $v_i < v_r$, but that v_i appears leftmost of v_r in $\Delta(v_j, v_k)$. However, both formulations are equivalent as they avoid redundant computations. The used formulation is easier to comprehend, while the formulation in the code base can be computed more

efficiently.

$$M_{\blacklozenge} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{v_k \in \Delta(v_i, v_j)} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \\ \Delta(v_j, v_k): \\ v_i < v_r}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left(t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_k), \frac{\mathcal{W}_{t_0|\{\tau(v_j), \tau(v_k)\}}(v_i, v_r)}{2} \right)$$

All typed chordal wedge collisions \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}| \cdot \Delta_{\max}^2 \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|)$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles that an edge is adjacent to in the graph.

D.18 Wheel

The wheel graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} . The computation of M_{\blacklozenge} differs from the provided code to improve readability. It does not explicitly create the set of all diamonds in which nodes participate, but rather assumes it is present. Further, the code base does not assume that $v_i < v_r$, but that v_i appears leftmost of v_r in $\Delta(v_j, v_k)$. However, both formulations are equivalent as they avoid redundant computations. The used formulation is easier to comprehend, while the formulation in the code base can be computed more efficiently.

$$M_{\blacklozenge} := \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \\ \Delta(v_i, v_j): \\ v_i < v_k}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \\ \Delta(v_j, v_k): \\ v_i < v_r}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M \left(\tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), t_0, \tau(v_r), t_0, \left(\mathcal{D}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j, v_r) \right) \right) \\ \oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_1 < t_2}} M(\tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), t_0, \tau(v_r), t_1), \mathcal{D}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j, v_r) \cdot \mathcal{D}_{t_1}(v_i, v_j, v_r))$$

All wheels \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|E| \cdot \Delta_{\max}^2 \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|^2)$ time, where Δ_{\max} denotes the maximum number of triangles that an edge is adjacent to in the graph.

D.19 Hatted 4-Clique

The hatted 4-clique graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} . The negative terms in the beginning of the equation M_{\blacklozenge} account for overcounting of hatted-4-cliques by 4-clique graphlets, similar to the additional correction terms for other graphlets.

Further, the computation of M_{\blacklozenge} differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code base creates a data structure containing all nodes $v_k \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$ with $(v_i, v_j) < (v_i, v_k)$ that are connected to v_j to efficiently retrieve v_k . M_{\blacklozenge} assumes $v_k \in \Delta(v_i, v_j)$ with $v_i < v_k$ and $v_j < v_k$ for readability. $(v_i, v_j) < (v_i, v_k)$ and $v_j < v_k$ both ensure that each combination of nodes

v_j and v_k is only considered once, where the first is easier to implement and the second is easier to read. The code base uses the same structure to efficiently retrieve nodes v_r forming 4-cliques with v_i, v_j and v_r , where $v_k < v_r$ is equivalent to the position of v_k being before the position of v_r in the data structure, as both conditions avoid consideration of duplicates. Also, the code directly retrieves the type t_0 of the triangle together with the count from a data structure.

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\blacklozenge} := & \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \Delta(v_i, v_j): \\ v_i < v_k \\ v_j < v_k}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \mathcal{C}(v_i, v_j, v_k): \\ v_k < v_r}} \\
& M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_j)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_k)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_j), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_j)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k)), -1) \\
& \oplus M((\tau(v_r), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_r)), -1) \\
& \oplus \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), t_0), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_j)) \\
& \quad \oplus M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_r), t_0), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_k)) \\
& \quad \oplus M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), t_0), \Delta_{t_0}(v_i, v_r)) \\
& \quad \oplus M((\tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_r), t_0), \Delta_{t_0}(v_j, v_k)) \\
& \quad \oplus M((\tau(v_j), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_k), t_0), \Delta_{t_0}(v_j, v_r)) \\
& \quad \oplus M((\tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), t_0), \Delta_{t_0}(v_j, v_r))
\end{aligned}$$

All typed hatted 4-cliques \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{W}_{\vec{\Delta}}| + DD \cdot |\mathcal{T}_V|)$ time, where DD is the number of directed diamonds as described in [18].

D.20 Almost 5-Clique

The almost 5-clique graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} . The computation of M_{\blacklozenge} differs from the provided code to improve readability. The code uses $v_j \in \mathcal{N}(v_i)$ followed by a check if $\deg(i) > \deg(j)$ or if $\deg(i) = \deg(j)$ and $i > j$ as the index of the undirected edge is needed. This formula simplifies this notation by choosing $v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)$. M_{\blacklozenge} also assumes Δ and \mathcal{C} to be present while

the code base needs to initialize them.

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\blacklozenge} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \Delta(v_i, v_j): \\ v_i < v_k < v_j}} \sum_{t_0 \in \mathcal{T}_V} \\
&M \left((t_0, t_0, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k)), \binom{\mathcal{C}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j, v_k)}{2} \right) \\
&\oplus \sum_{\substack{t_1 \in \mathcal{T}_V: \\ t_0 < t_1}} M((t_0, t_1, \tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k)), \mathcal{C}_{t_0}(v_i, v_j, v_k) \cdot \mathcal{C}_{t_1}(v_i, v_j, v_k))
\end{aligned}$$

All typed almost 5-cliques can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(|\Delta| \cdot (\deg_{\max} + |\mathcal{T}_V|^2))$ time.

D.21 5-Clique

The 5-clique graphlet is computed by the count map M_{\blacklozenge} . The computation of M_{\blacklozenge} differs from the provided code to improve readability. M_{\blacklozenge} assumes Δ and \mathcal{C} to be present while the code base needs to initialize them. While the code again considers $(v_i, v_j) < (v_i, v_k)$, M_{\blacklozenge} abbreviates this by $v_j < v_k$ as explained above. $v_l \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_r)$ is a similar combination from the conditions that an edge between v_r and v_l exists and that the position of v_l is to the right of the position of v_r in $\mathcal{C}(v_i, v_j, v_l)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\blacklozenge} &:= \sum_{v_i \in V} \sum_{v_j \in \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_i)} \sum_{\substack{v_k \in \Delta(v_i, v_j): \\ v_i < v_k \\ v_j < v_k}} \sum_{\substack{v_r \in \mathcal{C}(v_i, v_j, v_k) \\ v_r < v_k}} \sum_{\substack{v_l \in \mathcal{C}(v_i, v_j, v_l) \\ \cap \vec{\mathcal{N}}(v_r)}} \\
&M((\tau(v_i), \tau(v_j), \tau(v_k), \tau(v_r), \tau(v_l)), 1)
\end{aligned}$$

All typed 5-cliques \blacklozenge can be counted in $\mathcal{O}(DBP + D + |\Delta| + |V| + |E|)$ time, where DBP denotes the number of directed bipyramids as described in [18] and D describes the number of diamonds \blacklozenge .